

BY-COVID Data Mobilisation Preprint (V4.0)

Advancing Data Mobilisation for Pandemic Preparedness in Health Science

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Introduction

In the wake of recent global health crises, particularly the COVID-19 pandemic, the essential role of data mobilisation in health science for pandemic preparedness has become increasingly evident. Rapid and efficient access to relevant data is paramount for generating and sharing knowledge, timely decision-making, resource allocation, and the development of effective interventions. Preparedness has gained prominence in high-level policy, with UNESCO establishing a working group to extend its Open Science Toolkit by including guidance and tools for data policy in times of crises ([Data Policy for Times of Crisis \(DPTC\) - CODATA, Committee on Data of the ISC](#)). This paper aims to advance data mobilisation strategies for pandemic preparedness by:

1. Exploring and illustrating key interdisciplinary actions that enhance data mobilisation.
2. Benchmarking data mobilisation efficiency through expert experiences from the BY-COVID project and relevant case studies in the context of pandemic preparedness.
3. Proposing recommendations to streamline and facilitate data mobilisation efforts.

A central goal is to **raise awareness** among stakeholders (including funding bodies, researchers, governmental agencies, and policymakers) about the importance of data mobilisation in infectious diseases research and pandemic preparedness. Fostering a culture of data sharing and collaboration can help stakeholders recognise the collective benefits of data mobilisation efforts and commit to supporting them. Beyond sensitising data holders and permitting authorities, science actors must also be encouraged to prioritise rapid-cycle evidence generation to inform policy, bioethics committees, and clinical decisions. This requires adapting agendas, methods, and tools to meet public needs. Functional, adaptive, and sustainable data platforms, along with dedicated data stewards and trainers, are fundamental to improving the efficiency and quality of data mobilisation. Consequently, a long-term funding strategy to sustain and advance these efforts is necessary.

Acknowledging the contributions of individual researchers and data providers (especially those facilitating data mobilisation) is crucial, as their expertise strengthens pandemic preparedness efforts. Incorporating insights from data experts into data mobilisation strategies ensures a holistic approach to addressing public health challenges.

A **multi-tiered data mobilisation framework** requires well-supported Research Infrastructures (RIs) such as GenBank, the European Genome-Phenome Archive (EGA), and local pathogen data hubs/platforms based on both centralised and federated repositories for pandemic-related data. Ensuring these existing RIs remain adaptable is essential for responding to future public health challenges. Public health institutions and laboratories, such as the [Sweden SciLifeLab](#), [Sciensano](#) in Belgium, or [BIGAN](#) in Aragon (Spain), significantly contribute to efficient data mobilisation due to their close connection to pandemic response efforts.

At the European and national/regional levels, surveillance networks reinforce pandemic preparedness. For instance, the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) actively supports data mobilisation, providing extensive [data, dashboards, and databases](#). The [EU/EEA routine surveillance open data policy](#) supports transparency and

accessibility in pandemic surveillance. Additionally, it coordinates surveillance efforts across Europe, while national initiatives such as Sciensano's dashboard and open data portal ([Epistat – COVID-19 Monitoring](#)) contribute valuable insights.

Sufficiently standardised metadata and adequate provenance information are essential for transparent, traceable and effective data mobilisation (Ohmann *et al.*, 2024). Ensuring that datasets are linked to key contextual information (e.g., study protocols, consent forms, and data management plans) strengthens their usability.

Compliance with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016) is fundamental to ensuring data accessibility and reuse. However, long-term compliance requires careful selection of technical solutions, such as robust computing frameworks, services, and sustainable storage architecture. Although Electronic Medical Records (EMR) and Electronic Health Records (EHR) were originally developed for clinical and administrative purposes, they are increasingly used in research. Nevertheless, challenges remain in aligning them with FAIR principles, and efforts are underway to improve their usability in research contexts (Dugas *et al.*, 2024).

Given the sensitive nature of health data, compliance with legal and regulatory frameworks (linked to multiple administrative and executive levels), particularly the **European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**, is essential. Recognising national and regional variations in GDPR implementation is necessary to facilitate cross-border data sharing while ensuring privacy safeguards. The [European Health Data Space Regulation \(EHDS\)](#) oversees the secure and efficient secondary use of health data across Member States, promoting interoperability and streamlining data mobilisation. Moreover, intermediary institutions referenced in the [Data Governance Act](#) play a crucial role in preparing and structuring datasets for broader use, while specialised regulations such as the [Artificial Intelligence Act](#) address ethical and legal considerations in AI-driven health data processing.

A case study-driven approach enables the systematic documentation of data mobilisation challenges and the assessment of methods used to analyse and address them. Identifying bottlenecks and best practices can help refine existing data mobilisation support and frameworks, informing future strategies and investments.

Key elements of an efficient data mobilisation process include i) reinforcing infrastructure support (such as metadata repositories, data curation centres) and ii) addressing barriers (including data access restrictions and de-identification challenges).

Any recommendation for data mobilisation should highlight **clear incentives for stakeholders**, ensuring that data sharing is perceived as beneficial and leveraged effectively. Research funders and policymakers can mandate sharing, journal editors can facilitate rapid dissemination, and patients and citizens can actively contribute to data collection. Addressing researchers' concerns, such as recognition, funding, and support for data preparation (e.g. anonymisation and legal agreements), is key to fostering participation. From data producers to end-users, stakeholders stand to gain insights, resources, and collaborations that strengthen the readiness for global health crises.

Anticipating and addressing key challenges, including data security risks and interoperability barriers, is crucial for the effective implementation of data mobilisation recommendations. **Recommendations** should be strategically tailored to mitigate these challenges and foster a sustainable ecosystem for data sharing and collaboration.

In the upcoming years, data mobilisation will continue to evolve under the **framework of the EHDS Regulation**, which was published in the Official Journal of the European Union on 5 March 2025. Several projects, notably the TEHDAS2 Joint Action (www.tehdas.eu) and [QUANTUM](#), will offer ongoing **guidance on data governance**, data access procedures, secure processing, and devolution, contributing to the implementation of the EHDS Regulation. In particular, significant efforts from the TEHDAS Joint Action have defined the expected data lifecycle to shape the narrative around data mobilisation within the HealthData@EU infrastructure, aimed at supporting the secondary use of health data under the EHDS.

Overall, these actions highlight the necessity of well-defined metadata catalogues, standardised data access forms and management systems, and a cohesive approach to constructing secure processing environments. The Strategic Agenda for the Health Research and Innovation Cloud (Canham *et al.*, 2023, <https://zenodo.org/records/10231556>), generated as part of the [HealthyCloud](#) project, proposed a series of shared services among research infrastructures to strengthen data mobilisation, including existing research landscaping, legal and regulatory contexts, and best practices for using data and metadata standards. Additionally, it underscores the strategic need to align the HealthData@EU infrastructure with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), as well as major RIs. By aligning with HealthData@EU principles and provisions, stakeholders, particularly RIs and researchers, can ensure compliance with regulatory requirements while maximising data reuse and transparency.

In this paper, by enhancing awareness, benchmarking efficiency, and establishing comprehensive guidelines, we aim to unlock the full potential of data mobilisation to mitigate the impact of future health crises and safeguard public health globally. Importantly, this is not necessarily confined to infectious disease outbreaks and especially pandemic preparedness; the recommendations developed can be extended to other fields. For example, the secondary use of health data could significantly benefit rare disease research, precision medicine, the European Initiative to UNderstand CANcer (Uncan.eu), and environmental monitoring.